

ISSUES OF RESEARCH AND PUBLICATION OF SOURCES RELATED TO ISLAMIC SCIENCES

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Abstract: Historically, Islamic studies as a field of science have been formed in Europe since the middle Ages. The main goal of this field of science was to study the essence of the religious belief that arose in the Middle East and was foreign to Europeans and, if necessary, try to determine ways to compete with it. As a result, in order to study the Qur'an, which is the main source of Islam, they first translated it into various European languages. After all, this religion, which was getting stronger year by year, reaching new areas, and conquering new milestones, literally worried them.

Keywords: Holy Qur'an, Islamic studies, scientific institutions, Islamic religion, explanatory translations.

Introduction

In this way, the field of Islamic studies, which studies the Islamic religion in various directions, such as its sources, history, philosophy, culture, economy, and serves to form one's own attitudes towards it, was born and has been fulfilling its mission for centuries. Therefore, even today, two types of western and eastern approaches are preserved in the study of the Islamic religion and the fields of science formed on its basis, as well as the history and culture of Islam in general.

On the eve of independence, in 1989, the "Group for the preparation of the scientific and explanatory academic edition of the Holy Qur'an in Uzbek" was established under the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan with the task of preparing a scientific and explanatory academic edition of the Holy Qur'an in Uzbek. As a result of the work of the group, the first part of the academic translation of the "Quran Karim" in Uzbek with scientific explanation, i.e. 15 volumes, was prepared [21].

In the next period, in the researches in the field of Islamic studies, attention was also paid to the way of putting the sources of Islamic sciences into scientific circulation by creating scientific and explanatory translations. In 2000, the first volume of "al-Hidaya" was translated into Uzbek and published for the first time [8].

The Main Findings and Results

Today, the research activity of sources related to Islamic sciences at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan can be conditionally divided into six directions.

The first is case studies. Among the works carried out in this direction, the research of the history of the formation of the Ferghana school of jurisprudence [19: 17], the study of the development of Hanafi doctrine in our region [14: 15], the analysis of the religious situation in the Koqan khanate [7] and the research on the history of Sufism in Transoxiana can be cited as examples.

The second direction is the introduction of manuscript sources related to Islamic sciences into scientific circulation in the form of scientific critical texts and facsimile publications. Usually, the work in this field takes a lot of time, sometimes it takes years to achieve the result. Among the works carried out in recent years at the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan, we can mention the scientific and critical text of a rare source on the science of heritage in Arabic [10: 12], as well as facsimile editions of a manuscript that has reached our time only in a single copy, which embodies a number of fields of Islamic sciences [15: 105].

The third direction is to create a catalog of manuscripts of works and documents related to Islamic sciences. One of the first works carried out in the years of independence related to the manuscripts of judicial documents stored in the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan [11]. Another remarkable aspect of the implementation of this work is that it was carried out in cooperation with Japanese experts. In cooperation with foreign source experts, first a short [13], then a second complete catalog of the manuscripts of Sufism works was created [12]. It is noteworthy that this catalog was prepared in cooperation with German experts.

While there is a certain experience in creating a catalog of the works of famous scholars in the field of textual studies, the practice of creating a catalog of manuscripts of the works of scholars of a particular region is not widespread. However, based on the place of the scientific heritage of Termiz scholars in the spiritual and cultural development of our region, two catalogs of manuscripts of their works were prepared and published [17;18].

The fourth direction is the preparation of scientific and explanatory translation publications of sources related to Islamic sciences.

During 2015-2017, a scientific and explanatory translation of 12 works of Termizian scholars from Arabic and Persian into Uzbek was prepared and published.

Among the works included in the scientific circulation is the Mazu of etiquette ethics [22; 23; 26], about the history of fulfilling the pillars of the Islamic religion [24], about the criteria of halal-haram, goodness, humaneness, honest work, professional virtue defined in the Islamic religion [2; 25; 26], books dedicated to the history of Islam [1] took place. In addition, works on Sufism [27], history of statehood [28], medieval literature [3] were published.

During 2018-20, research was carried out within the framework of the practical project on the topic "Research and publication of sources related to Islamic sciences". Within the framework of the project, the science of jurisprudence of our scholars who came from our country [9; 4] and works on Sufism [23] were published, and a scientific-explanatory translation from Persian of the work "Mujarrabot" on the science of medicine was prepared for publication.

The fifth direction is research and publication of documents. As the work done in this field, we can mention the works called "Register of Judges in Colonial Turkestan, 1887" [5] and "Собрание фетв по обоснованию зикра джахр и сама" ("Complex of fatwas justifying Zikri jahriy and samo"). [6].

The sixth direction is related to the application of scientific innovation and information obtained from the research of sources related to Islamic sciences to the educational process. As a result of the active participation of the institute's scientists in the integration with higher education, textbooks and training manuals are created and applied to the educational processes of higher education [4; 16; 20].

Conclusion

In short, we believe that in addition to the fact that the Institute of Oriental Studies of the Academy of Sciences of the Republic of Uzbekistan has gained a certain experience in conducting research on Islamic sciences, it is necessary to strengthen the cooperation between scientific institutions in order to increase the efficiency and scientific level of these works. At the same time, in this process, in our opinion, it is necessary to take into account our local and national characteristics, creatively using world experience, foreign scientific methodology and best practices. One of the important tasks ahead of us is to accelerate the activity of conveying the results of academic researches and the content of scientific sources to our people in simple and popular forms.

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